

Holmskioldia sanguinea: The coarsely powdered plant material (1 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether and benzene over steam bath for 3×12 hr, separately. Both the extracts were mixed together, being similar in tlc behaviour, and chromatographed over silica gel when the following compounds were obtained.

Docasane, tetracosanol, friedelin and friedelinol were identified by comparison with authentic samples and by preparing their suitable derivatives.

Wogonin: It is a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 203-04°. It gave colour with FeCl₃ and positive Wilson's boric test. Elemental analysis and mass measurements (284, M⁺) assigned⁹ its molecular formula as C₁₆H₁₂O₆. UV λ_{max}^{MeOH}: 270, 330 nm.

IR ν_{max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹: 3400-3200 (O-H stretch hydrogen bonded), 1660 (C=O stretch), 1610 and 1580. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone D₆): δ 3.97 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.32 (1H, s, C-6H), 6.82 (1H, s, C-3H), 11.31 [1H, s (br), C-5 OH], 9.4 (1H, s, C-7 OH), 8.13 (2H, dd, C-2', 6' protons), 7.63 (3H, m, C-3', 4', 5' protons). The above data indicated the compound to be 5,7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy flavone (wogonin), finally confirmed by preparation of its diacetate, m.p. 151° and comparison with an authentic sample.

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Possible Anthelmintic Compounds. Part-II : Mannich Bases from 2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(aryl/alkyl- benzimidazolyl)-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones

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SUBSTITUTED quinazolones¹⁻³ and benzimidazoles^{4,5} have been found to possess high anthelmintic activity. These observations have prompted the authors to synthesise a series of new compounds having both the quinazolone and benzimidazole moieties in their molecules and to evaluate their anthelmintic activity.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

2-Aryl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinone (I): These were prepared by the action of anthranilic acids⁶⁻⁹ and acid chlorides in presence of pyridine^{10,11} and substituted anthranils were obtained by following the published work¹².

2-Aryl/alkyl-2-alkyl/phenyl carboxy substituted quinazolone (II): A mixture of 2-substituted benzoxazinones (0.01 mole) and amino acids (0.01 mole) in dry pyridine was refluxed at 150° for 6 hr. Pyridine was removed by washing with dil. HCl (5 N) and the residue was extracted with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃. Crude product (II) obtained on acidification was purified by recrystallization from aqueous ethanol.

2-Alkyl/aryl 3-[2'-alkyl/aryl-benzimidazolyl]-3,1(4H)quinazolinones (III): They were obtained by the condensation of II and *o*-phenylenediamine in presence of excess of polyphosphoric acid¹³.

Mannich bases of 2-alkyl/aryl 3-[2'-alkyl/aryl-benzimidazolyl]-3,1(4H)quinazolin-4-one (IV): A mixture of III (0.01 mole), an amine (0.015 mole) and formalin (0.25 mole; 40%) was refluxed in ethanol for 10 hr. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

Bio-assay :

LD₅₀ for the compounds was determined¹⁴ and was found to be in the order of 680-700 mg/kg of the animals (rat). The compounds were screened for their anthelmintic activity against *H. nana*¹⁵ and *N. brasiliensis*¹⁶.

Results and Discussion

The compounds were found to be well tolerated and were devoid of any toxic manifestation. Substitution of morpholine, piperidine and pyrrolidine residue resulted in compounds with high activity.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF MANNICH BASES OF 2-ALKYL/ARYL-3-BENZIMIDAZOLYLQUINAZOLIN-4(3H)-ONES (IV) AND THEIR ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Inhibition	
							<i>H. nana</i>	<i>N. brasiliensis</i>
1*	C ₆ H ₅	I	— piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	172-75	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OI	99	37
2.	C ₆ H ₅	I	— morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	168-70	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₂ I	—	—
3.	C ₆ H ₅	I	— N—CH ₃ — piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	249-50	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OI	—	—
4.	C ₆ H ₅	I	— 4—CH ₃ — piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	220-24	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ OI	—	—
5*	C ₆ H ₅	Br	— piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	223-25	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OBr	50	36
6*	C ₆ H ₅	Br	— morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	197-200	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OBr	Inactive	Inactive
7.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	— N—CH ₃ — piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	249-51	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OBr	—	—
8.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	— 4—CH ₃ — piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	220	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ OBr	—	—
9.	C ₆ H ₅	H	— piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	185	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ O	—	—
10*	C ₆ H ₅	H	— morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	189-90	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₂	71	39
11*	C ₆ H ₅	H	— pyrrolidine	C ₆ H ₄	179-80	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₅ O	57	Inactive
12.	C ₆ H ₅	H	— 4—CH ₃ — piperidine	CH ₂ —C ₆ H ₅	110	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ N ₆ O	—	—
13.	C ₆ H ₅	H	— piperidine	—CH—COOH CH ₂ —C ₆ H ₅	215-17	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₆ O	—	—
14.	<i>o</i> -Nitro-phenoxy	H	— piperidine	—CH—COOH C ₆ H ₄	140-42	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂	50	Inactive
15.	<i>o</i> -Nitro-phenoxy	H	— morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	195-97	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂	—	—
16*	—CH ₃	H	— morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	215-17	C ₂₇ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₂	64	—
17*	—OH ₂	H	— piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	268	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ N ₆ O	50	43
18.	—CH ₃	H	— N(OH ₂) ₂	C ₆ H ₄	255-56	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ N ₆ O	43	35

Infrared data : Disappearance of a peak between 1850-1587 cm⁻¹ for C=O group indicates the formation of benzimidazole ring and utilization of acid carboxylic group.

Analytical data : C, H and N were found within the range of experimental error.

* Screened for anthelmintic activity.

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Thin Layer Chromatographic Analysis and Characterisation of Some Substituted Maleianilic Acids

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SUBBA Rao¹ characterized some aromatic primary amines as a derivative of corresponding phthalianilic acid. In the present study twelve maleianilic acids were prepared and characterized by melting

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